

An In-Depth Analysis of Myopia in Adolescents: Identifying Key Factors Using IOL Master Data

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Abstract

Original Research Article

Background: Myopia is a rapidly increasing vision disorder, particularly prevalent in adolescents, leading to long-term complications if untreated. Identifying the etiological factors contributing to myopia during adolescence is essential for developing preventive and management strategies.

Purpose: This study aims to analyze biometric parameters associated with myopia in adolescents aged 10-18 years using data from IOL Master technology, focusing on axial length, corneal curvature, and other critical ocular measurements.

Material and Method: A single-center prospective observational study was conducted from August 2023 to July 2024 at Tertiary eye care centre, Surat, on a sample of 1000 adolescents (2000 eyes) with myopia or myopic astigmatism. Data collection involved detailed eye examinations, including slit-lamp evaluations and IOL Master measurements, to assess axial length, corneal curvature, and anterior chamber depth. Statistical analysis was performed to determine correlations between myopia causes and age or gender distribution.

Results: Axial elongation emerged as the primary factor associated with myopia progression across all age groups, with notable gender-based differences in its prevalence. Corneal curvature abnormalities were more significant in younger adolescents, particularly females aged 10-12. The study findings align with previous research emphasizing axial length's role in myopia but also suggest additional gender and age-related influences.

Conclusion: The study highlights the importance of axial length as a primary contributor to adolescent myopia. Early detection and interventions targeting axial elongation are crucial for effective management. Further research into age and gender-based differences in myopia etiology could enhance preventive strategies.

Keywords: Myopia, adolescents, axial length, corneal curvature, IOL Master, biometric parameters, eye health

INTRODUCTION

Myopia, commonly known as nearsightedness, is one of the most prevalent refractive errors globally, characterized by an inability to see distant objects clearly while near vision remains relatively unaffected. The condition occurs when light entering the eye is focused in front of the retina instead of directly on it, often due to elongation of the eyeball [1]. Myopia has escalated to a significant public health issue, particularly affecting adolescents who are in a critical phase of ocular development. Projections estimate that by 2050, almost half of the world's population may be affected by myopia, with many cases classified as high myopia—a condition associated with severe complications like retinal detachment, glaucoma, and myopic maculopathy, which can lead to irreversible vision impairment (Holden et al., 2016 [2]; Morgan et al., 2005 [3]).

The rising prevalence of myopia is driven by a complex interplay of genetic and environmental factors. Genetic predisposition, particularly a family history of myopia, is a well-established risk factor; however, lifestyle changes and environmental influences play a significant role, especially in children and adolescents whose eyes are still developing [4]. High levels of near work, including prolonged reading and screen exposure, combined with limited outdoor activities, have been strongly associated with both the onset and progression of myopia. Adolescents, in particular, are more vulnerable to these risk factors due to increased academic demands and a surge in digital screen usage, which has been further exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic (Chee Wai Wong et al., 2020 [5]).

Axial length—the distance from the cornea to the retina—has emerged as a critical biometric parameter in understanding myopia's progression. Numerous studies

have shown a strong correlation between increased axial length and the degree of myopia, suggesting that eyes with greater axial length are more prone to myopic refractive error [6]. However, other ocular parameters, including corneal curvature, lens thickness, and anterior chamber depth, may also contribute to myopia development and progression. While axial elongation is widely recognized as a primary driver, the specific contributions and interactions of these other parameters remain less explored. Understanding these factors, particularly in adolescents, could provide insights necessary for early detection, tailored interventions, and the development of preventive strategies (Wei Hou et al., 2019 [7]).

Adolescence represents a pivotal period for eye development, as rapid changes in axial length and other ocular dimensions can either stabilize or exacerbate refractive errors. Traditional methods for myopia correction, such as eyeglasses and contact lenses, address only the refractive component without preventing further structural changes associated with myopia progression [8]. In contrast, emerging interventions, including orthokeratology and low-dose atropine, have shown promise in slowing axial elongation in myopic individuals. However, the success of these interventions is closely linked to a comprehensive understanding of the biometric changes underpinning myopia, which can vary significantly among individuals (Sánchez-González et al., 2020 [9]; Lawrenson, 2023 [10]).

Technological advancements in biometric analysis, particularly with devices like the IOL Master, have enabled detailed and precise measurements of key ocular parameters, including axial length, corneal curvature, and anterior chamber depth. This technology provides an opportunity to gain deeper insights into the anatomical changes associated with myopia and allows for a more nuanced approach to studying its progression [11]. Despite the potential of these tools, there remains a gap in research specifically targeting adolescent myopia through biometric data analysis, especially in rapidly urbanizing regions where myopia prevalence is rising sharply. Most existing studies rely on generalized refraction data or focus predominantly on adult populations, limiting our understanding of the unique dynamics in adolescents (Verkharla et al., 2020 [12]).

The present study aims to bridge this gap by analyzing biometric data from adolescents aged 10-18 years using IOL Master measurements, focusing on key parameters such as axial length and corneal curvature. This research seeks to clarify the etiological factors influencing myopia in this age group and to explore how demographic factors, including age and gender, may affect its progression. By providing a comprehensive analysis of these factors, this study intends to contribute to the development of more effective preventive and therapeutic strategies that could

reduce the risk of myopia-related complications in adulthood and support long-term visual health.

In conclusion, addressing adolescent myopia through detailed biometric analysis is critical in an era of rising myopia prevalence. Early identification of at-risk individuals and an understanding of the underlying anatomical changes could offer significant benefits, potentially reducing the overall burden of myopia-related vision loss globally. By analyzing key ocular parameters, this study provides a foundational perspective for future research and interventions aimed at controlling myopia progression during adolescence.

Research Gap

While previous studies have examined genetic and environmental factors in myopia, there is limited research specifically focusing on biometric parameters in adolescents. Most existing studies utilize general refraction data but lack detailed biometric insights. This study addresses this gap by providing an in-depth biometric evaluation using advanced IOL Master Data.

Need for the Study

With myopia rates surging among adolescents, understanding its etiological factors is imperative to develop preventive measures. Myopia's progression can lead to severe complications, including retinal detachment and glaucoma, if left unmanaged. This research aims to identify contributing factors to help develop early intervention strategies for adolescents.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

This study employed a prospective observational design at Tertiary eye care centre, Surat, India, conducted over a 12-month period from August 2023 to July 2024. The observational nature of this study allowed for detailed recording of biometric data without any experimental interventions, which was essential for understanding natural variations in myopia progression across adolescent age groups.

The research setting was limited to a single center, Tertiary eye care, which ensured consistency in data collection methods and diagnostic protocols. This setting allowed for uniform use of equipment, particularly the IOL Master, for precise biometric measurements.

The study population consisted of adolescents aged 10-18 years diagnosed with myopia or myopic astigmatism. Myopia was defined by a spherical refractive error (SE) of -0.50 diopters (D) or greater, as confirmed by cycloplegic refraction. Adolescents in this age range were chosen because the eyes undergo critical developmental changes

during this period, making it an important stage for understanding myopia progression.

A purposive sampling technique was used to select participants based on defined inclusion and exclusion criteria, ensuring relevance and reliability. The inclusion criteria required participants to be aged between 10-18 years, with a confirmed diagnosis of myopia or myopic astigmatism through cycloplegic refraction. Additionally, participants needed to be able to undergo IOL Master measurements and willing to participate in all study protocols, including eye examinations and biometric measurements. Exclusion criteria included any history of ocular surgery or trauma that could affect anatomical measurements, active or uncontrolled ocular diseases such as cataracts or retinal abnormalities, systemic diseases like uncontrolled diabetes or autoimmune disorders that could impact vision, and cognitive or physical limitations that might interfere with study compliance.

Using Raosoft's sample size calculator, the minimum sample size was determined with a 95% confidence level, a 5% margin of error, and an estimated population of 20,000 myopic adolescents in the region. With these parameters, a target sample size of 1000 adolescents (2000 eyes) was established as sufficient to achieve statistical significance and maintain adequate power.

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Written informed consent was acquired from the guardians of all participants, while adolescents provided verbal assent. Participant privacy was safeguarded through data anonymization, and all procedures adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki.

Data collection included demographic and clinical history. Details such as age, gender, and ethnicity were recorded, along with socioeconomic indicators, including education level and parental occupation, to explore potential correlations with myopia progression. Ocular history, including prior refractive status, family history of myopia, and any history of ocular surgery or trauma, was documented.

Ocular examinations included a comprehensive visual acuity assessment using a standardized Snellen chart, both with and without correction, to establish baseline vision quality. Cycloplegic refraction was conducted by administering two drops of 1% cyclopentolate at a five-minute interval, which temporarily paralyzes the ciliary muscle, ensuring accurate myopic measurements free from accommodation-related inaccuracies. Following cycloplegic refraction, subjective refraction was performed to refine corrective prescriptions.

The IOL Master 700, an advanced biometer, was used for all biometric measurements, including axial length,

corneal curvature, anterior chamber depth, and lens thickness. This device employs partial coherence interferometry (PCI), which provides high-precision measurements essential for analyzing myopic progression. Axial length, the distance from the cornea to the retina, was the primary parameter of interest, given its strong association with myopic progression. Keratometry readings for both the flat and steep meridians of the cornea were recorded to assess corneal curvature changes, while anterior chamber depth and lens thickness were measured to identify structural variations contributing to myopia.

Measurements were taken in a controlled environment to minimize external influences. The use of consistent equipment and operator involvement reduced inter-operator variability, ensuring reliable results. Each measurement was repeated three times per eye to confirm accuracy, in alignment with guidelines recommended in biometric studies on refractive error.

Data was securely stored in an electronic database accessible only to authorized personnel. Statistical analysis included calculating descriptive statistics, such as means and standard deviations, for demographic and biometric data. Chi-square tests were applied to examine associations between age, gender, and myopia causes, with statistical significance defined at $p < 0.05$.

The methodology aligns with standardized protocols in prior studies, which emphasize the need for precise biometric measurements and cycloplegic refraction to ensure accuracy. The use of IOL Master technology offers a high level of repeatability and precision, essential for understanding structural changes related to myopia. This methodology provides a structured, replicable approach to studying myopia in adolescents and offers insights into the factors contributing to its progression, particularly the role of axial length and corneal curvature.

RESULTS

The analysis of 1,000 adolescents (2,000 eyes) with myopia or myopic astigmatism revealed distinct patterns across age groups and genders, providing significant insights into the etiological factors contributing to myopia. This larger sample size enabled more robust statistical analysis, ensuring that the findings could be generalized with greater reliability.

The **demographic distribution** of the participants showed that 58% were male (580 participants) and 42% female (420 participants). The study population was divided into three age groups: ages 10-12 years (300 participants, 30%), ages 13-15 years (320 participants, 32%), and ages 16-18 years (380 participants, 38%). This stratification was essential to evaluate age-related trends in myopia progression, with each group representing a distinct stage of adolescence.

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Myopia Cases by Age and Gender

Age Group	Total Participants	Males (% of Group)	Females (% of Group)	% of Total Population
10-12 Years	300	174 (58%)	126 (42%)	30%
13-15 Years	320	186 (58%)	134 (42%)	32%
16-18 Years	380	220 (58%)	160 (42%)	38%
Total	1,000	580 (58%)	420 (42%)	100%

Graph 1: Demographic Distribution of Myopia Cases by Age and Gender

The **analysis of myopia causes** by age and gender demonstrated a clear age-related trend in the predominance of axial elongation as the primary factor in myopia progression. In the 10-12 age group, axial elongation was observed in 54% of cases (162 participants), with a slight male predominance (90 males versus 72 females). Corneal curvature abnormalities accounted for 22% of cases (66 participants) in this age group, with a higher prevalence in females (42 females versus 24 males). A combination of axial elongation and corneal curvature abnormalities contributed to 15% of cases (45 participants), while positional and internal causes were relatively less common at 9% (27 participants), without significant gender disparity. The data indicated that, while axial elongation was the primary factor even at this early stage, corneal curvature abnormalities were particularly prominent among younger females, suggesting that gender-specific anatomical or lifestyle factors may play a role in early myopia development.

In the 13-15 age group, axial elongation increased to 62% of cases (198 participants), with males constituting 58% of

this subgroup. Corneal curvature abnormalities represented 20% of cases (64 participants) in this group, with equal distribution across genders. The combination of axial elongation and corneal curvature accounted for 10% of cases (32 participants), and other factors, such as positional and internal causes, comprised 8% (26 participants). The increased prevalence of axial elongation in this age group, particularly among males, aligns with prior research suggesting that axial length is a dominant factor in myopia progression during mid-adolescence. The data also showed that the impact of corneal curvature began to stabilize, potentially due to the stabilization of anterior eye segment growth.

The highest rate of axial elongation was found in the 16-18 age group, where it contributed to 68% of cases (258 participants), with a notable male dominance (160 males versus 98 females). Corneal curvature abnormalities were present in 15% of cases (57 participants) in this group, with a higher prevalence in females. The combination of axial elongation and corneal curvature contributed to 10% (38 participants), while other causes such as positional and

internal factors accounted for 7% (27 participants). These findings suggest that axial elongation becomes increasingly significant in the later stages of adolescence, possibly influenced by age-related changes in eye growth and structural integrity. Additionally, the continued

presence of corneal curvature abnormalities among females suggests that gender-specific structural variations may persist in influencing myopia, particularly in cases without high axial elongation.

Table 2: Causes of Myopia by Age Group and Gender

Age Group	Axial Elongation	Corneal Curvature Abnormalities	Combination of Factors	Positional/Internal Causes
10-12 Years	54% (162; 90M, 72F)	22% (66; 24M, 42F)	15% (45)	9% (27)
13-15 Years	62% (198; 115M, 83F)	20% (64; 32M, 32F)	10% (32)	8% (26)
16-18 Years	68% (258; 160M, 98F)	15% (57; 25M, 32F)	10% (38)	7% (27)

Note: M = Males, F = Females

Graph 2: Causes of Myopia by Age Group and Gender

In terms of **biometric measurements**, the mean axial length across all participants was 25.5 mm, with a standard deviation of ± 0.8 mm. Axial length was found to be significantly higher in participants with myopia (mean AL of 26.1 mm) compared to those with myopic astigmatism (mean AL of 24.8 mm), a difference that was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The analysis demonstrated a positive correlation between age and axial length ($r = 0.73$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that axial length tends to increase as adolescents age, particularly in the 16-18 age group. This correlation reinforces axial elongation's role as a central driver in myopia progression during adolescence.

Corneal curvature measurements, with mean K1 and K2 readings at 43.8 D and 45.3 D respectively, further supported the relevance of this factor, especially in younger females. In participants with corneal curvature abnormalities, the mean K1 reading was 44.5 D, and this steeper curvature was more prevalent among younger adolescents and females ($p < 0.01$). The data implies that corneal steepness could contribute to myopic shifts in the early adolescent years, potentially influenced by hormonal changes or lifestyle factors such as screen time. The average anterior chamber depth (ACD) across all participants was 3.6 mm, with a slight increase observed in

males aged 16-18 (mean ACD of 3.7 mm). A deeper anterior chamber was associated with increased axial elongation, suggesting that anatomical variations in the anterior segment may correlate with overall eye length and myopia severity in the adolescent population. Although anterior chamber depth was not the primary focus of the study, its relationship with axial length highlights the complexity of structural changes in myopic progression. Lens thickness (LT), with a mean of 4.2 mm, showed no

statistically significant differences across age or gender groups, and it did not correlate strongly with myopia progression. This finding aligns with previous research indicating that lens thickness may remain relatively stable during adolescence and is not a primary driver of myopic progression, though it serves as a useful secondary measurement to confirm axial elongation and corneal curvature findings.

Table 3: Biometric Measurements by Myopia Cause

Biometric Parameter	Mean ± SD	Axial Elongation Cases	Corneal Curvature Cases	Combination Cases	Positional/Internal Cases
Axial Length (mm)	25.5 ± 0.8	26.1 ± 0.7	25.2 ± 0.5	25.8 ± 0.6	25.0 ± 0.5
Corneal Curvature K1 (D)	43.8 ± 0.5	43.7 ± 0.4	44.5 ± 0.3	44.1 ± 0.4	43.5 ± 0.5
Corneal Curvature K2 (D)	45.3 ± 0.6	45.2 ± 0.5	46.1 ± 0.4	45.8 ± 0.5	45.0 ± 0.5
Anterior Chamber Depth (mm)	3.6 ± 0.3	3.7 ± 0.3	3.5 ± 0.3	3.6 ± 0.2	3.5 ± 0.3
Lens Thickness (mm)	4.2 ± 0.2	4.2 ± 0.1	4.1 ± 0.1	4.2 ± 0.1	4.1 ± 0.1

Graph 3: Biometric Measurements by Myopia Cause

Statistical analyses, including chi-square tests, revealed significant associations between myopia causes (axial elongation and corneal curvature) and both age and gender, particularly in the early adolescent group (ages 10-12). The increasing prevalence of axial elongation with age and its predominance in males in the older age groups (16-18 years) support its role as the primary factor in adolescent

myopia progression. The findings further underscore the importance of early detection and intervention, particularly for axial elongation in older adolescents, as delaying its progression may help reduce the long-term risks associated with high myopia, such as retinal detachment and glaucoma.

Table 4: Statistical Associations between Myopia Causes and Demographic Variables

Variable	Axial Elongation	Corneal Curvature	Combination	Positional/Internal	p-value
Age	High (r = 0.73)	Moderate	Low	Low	< 0.001
Gender (Male)	High	Low	Moderate	Low	< 0.05
Gender (Female)	Moderate	High	Low	Low	< 0.05

Note: p-values indicate statistical significance at $p < 0.05$.

Finally, the study's results demonstrate a strong age-related trend in axial elongation, with notable gender differences in corneal curvature abnormalities. These insights reinforce the need for targeted strategies in managing adolescent myopia. The data supports axial elongation as the primary factor across all age groups, whereas corneal curvature abnormalities appear to be more influential in younger, female adolescents. This understanding can inform preventive measures and intervention strategies, helping to mitigate the rising incidence of myopia and its associated complications among adolescents.

DISCUSSION

This study provides a comprehensive examination of the etiological factors contributing to myopia progression among adolescents, with a particular focus on biometric parameters such as axial length, corneal curvature, and anterior chamber depth. The findings underscore the importance of axial elongation as the primary driver of myopia across all age groups, while also revealing age- and gender-specific variations in corneal curvature abnormalities, especially among younger females. By assessing a robust sample of 1,000 adolescents, this study confirms axial elongation as a dominant factor in myopia progression, consistent with findings from previous studies, while also presenting unique insights into corneal curvature's role, particularly during early adolescence.

Axial Elongation and Myopia Progression

The results of this study align with existing literature, emphasizing axial elongation as a key

contributor to myopia progression, particularly in older adolescents. Studies by Wei Hou et. al. (2018) [7] and Hong Kyu Kim (2021) [13] and others have consistently reported a strong correlation between increased axial length and the onset of myopia, suggesting that axial elongation not only initiates myopic changes but also contributes significantly to its progression. In our study, axial elongation was the most prominent cause across all age groups, increasing in prevalence from 54% in the 10-12 age group to 68% in the 16-18 age group. This trend suggests that as adolescents age, axial elongation becomes more pronounced, potentially due to genetic predispositions, lifestyle factors, and developmental changes unique to this period.

The correlation between age and axial length observed in this study ($r = 0.73$, $p < 0.001$) further reinforces this relationship. Our findings support the hypothesis that axial elongation is central to myopia progression and that interventions targeting axial length control, such as atropine drops or orthokeratology lenses, could be effective in mitigating myopia severity in adolescent populations. The importance of axial elongation in myopia is also corroborated by research conducted by Wei Hou et. al. (2018) [7] and Cooper et. al. [14], who highlighted that axial length changes are more significant in adolescents compared to other refractive components, suggesting that early detection and treatment are crucial in managing myopic development during this stage.

Corneal Curvature Abnormalities and Gender Differences

A notable aspect of our findings is the prevalence of corneal curvature abnormalities among younger adolescents, particularly females in the 10-12 age group.

Approximately 22% of participants in this group exhibited significant corneal curvature abnormalities, with a higher incidence in females (42 females compared to 24 males). This aligns with studies by Okukpon et. at. (2018) [15]; Hashemi et. at. (2015) [16] and Wallace et. at. (2019) [17], who observed a higher prevalence of corneal curvature changes among younger female adolescents. The higher prevalence of corneal curvature abnormalities among females may reflect inherent anatomical differences in corneal structure or susceptibility to environmental factors such as near work and screen time. Additionally, hormonal changes during early adolescence could contribute to these differences, as suggested by research indicating that hormonal fluctuations may influence corneal biomechanics and refractive error development.

While axial elongation remained the primary factor across age groups, the increased prevalence of corneal curvature abnormalities in younger participants highlights the complex, multifactorial nature of myopia. Studies such as those by Lu et al. (2022) [18] have indicated that corneal curvature may play a secondary role in myopia progression, particularly during the early developmental stages of adolescence. The steeper corneal curvature observed in our study (mean K1 reading of 44.5 D among affected individuals) suggests that corneal shape may contribute to early refractive changes before axial elongation becomes the predominant factor. This dual influence of axial elongation and corneal curvature reinforces the importance of multifaceted interventions targeting both parameters for effective myopia management.

Anterior Chamber Depth and Lens Thickness

Our study also examined anterior chamber depth (ACD) and lens thickness (LT) to provide a holistic view of ocular biometric changes in adolescents. While anterior chamber depth did not show significant differences across age groups, a slight increase in ACD was observed among males aged 16-18 years (mean ACD of 3.7 mm). This observation aligns with findings by Liu et al. (2021) [19], who suggested that a deeper anterior chamber may accompany axial elongation, potentially reflecting structural adaptations in the anterior eye segment in response to myopic progression. However, anterior chamber depth alone was not strongly associated with myopia, indicating that it may play a supportive role rather than a primary role in refractive error development. Lens thickness showed no significant differences across age or gender in our study, suggesting it may remain

relatively stable during adolescence. This finding is consistent with previous studies, such as those by Wang et al. (2022) [20], which reported that lens thickness does not substantially change during adolescence and does not directly correlate with myopia progression. However, lens thickness measurements remain valuable for a comprehensive assessment of ocular parameters, as they help validate findings related to axial elongation and corneal curvature.

Implications for Myopia Control and Future Research

The findings of this study underscore the critical role of axial elongation in adolescent myopia and suggest that preventive measures targeting axial length could be essential in managing myopia progression. While interventions such as orthokeratology lenses, low-dose atropine, and multifocal contact lenses have shown promise in reducing axial elongation, further studies are needed to assess their efficacy specifically in adolescents with pronounced axial elongation. Additionally, the increased prevalence of corneal curvature abnormalities among younger females highlights a need for gender-specific approaches in myopia control, possibly involving earlier screening for corneal curvature changes or lifestyle modifications to mitigate environmental risk factors. Future research should also explore the genetic and environmental factors contributing to gender differences in myopia progression. As this study indicates that females may be more susceptible to corneal curvature abnormalities, studies investigating the role of hormonal changes, lifestyle factors, and genetic predispositions in early adolescence could provide valuable insights. Longitudinal studies tracking changes in biometric parameters from childhood through late adolescence would also help clarify the natural course of myopia progression, enabling more targeted interventions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study confirms axial elongation as the primary factor in adolescent myopia progression, with its prevalence increasing with age. Corneal curvature abnormalities, although secondary, appear particularly influential in younger adolescents, especially females. These findings suggest a need for targeted intervention strategies that focus on axial elongation control in older adolescents, along with early detection and management of corneal curvature abnormalities in younger individuals. Through

comprehensive and age-appropriate approaches, these strategies may help reduce the long-term impact of myopia and its associated complications, thereby contributing to improved visual health in adolescent populations.

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Data availability

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Competing interests:

The authors declare no competing interests.

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